

New data on the spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of Dagestan, Russia

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Abstract

The study presents a list of 93 spider species collected in Dagestan, 12 of which are new records for the region. The following six species are illustrated: *Aelurillus laniger* Logunov & Marusik, 2000, *Arctosa personata* (L. Koch, 1872), *Arctosa ravidata* Ponomarev, 2007, *Clubiona caucasica* Mikhailov & Otto, 2017 and *Cyclosa algerica* Simon, 1885. I also provide photographs of live specimens for eight species, taken in their natural habitat, and present the first published photograph of the web of *Atypus muralis* Bertkau, 1890. Two species, *Aulonia kratochvili* Dunin, Buchar & Absolon, 1986 and *Cyclosa algerica*, are recorded for Russia for the first time; the former species is redescribed. A new species, *Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n. (Desidae), is described based on a female specimen. The family Desidae is reported from Russia for the first time. The current state of knowledge on the spider fauna of Dagestan and prospects for future research is discussed.

Keywords

Aranei, biodiversity, Desidae, Caucasus, fauna, new records, new species, redescription

Introduction

The Republic of Dagestan is a Russian region situated in the eastern part of the North Caucasus along the Caspian Sea. It is the southernmost part of Russia. Geographically, Dagestan is divided into a flat northern region and a mountainous southern one. The flat region includes the Kumyk Plain and the Nogai Steppe; this

area is beyond the scope of the present study. Prior to 2007, no dedicated studies of the spider fauna in Dagestan had been undertaken. Only fragmentary information was available, primarily comprising records of individual species and their descriptions (Abdurakhmanov et al. 2012). Systematic studies of the republic's araneofauna were subsequently initiated by Ponomarev and colleagues (Ponomarev & Khalidov 2007, Ponomarev & Alieva 2010, Ponomarev et al. 2011a; 2011b). The data obtained up to 2012 were summarized in a monograph dedicated to the spiders of Dagestan (Abdurakhmanov et al. 2012). This monograph records 397 species from 31 families within the republic. Subsequent research revealed 17 additional species in Dagestan (Ponomarev & Dvadnenko 2013, Ponomarev & Abdurakhmanov 2014; Ponomarev et al. 2017). A comprehensive faunistic study by Ponomarev et al. was published in 2019 (Ponomarev et al. 2019). The number of recorded spider species in Dagestan has thus increased to 460. Consequently, the number of spider species recorded in Dagestan surpasses that of neighboring regions in the North Caucasus (Ponomarev et al. 2019). However, Ponomarev et al. noted that Dagestan's diversity still lags behind that of neighboring Azerbaijan, a disparity that may reflect the incomplete study of the region's spider fauna. Following 2019, arachnological research has continued in the republic. Several new species from various families have been described (Ponomarev & Shmatko 2023, Ponomarev et al. 2024a, 2024b). Recent findings have not been limited to the description of new species. In the spring of 2021, I participated in an expedition to Dagestan. Although the field trip was brief, a substantial amount of material on the spider fauna was collected. The expedition resulted in the description of a new genus within the family Nesticidae (Fomichev et al. 2022). The remaining specimens from that field trip were unprocessed for a considerable time. This paper presents the findings from the analysis of these specimens, supplemented by material collected during a subsequent brief trip in late summer 2021. The aims of this paper are to: (1) provide a species list based on newly collected specimens; (2) report 12 species new to the fauna of Dagestan; (3) report two species and one family new to the fauna of Russia; (4) redescribe a poorly known species; and (5) describe the new species.

Materials and methods

This study is based on spider specimens collected by the author and colleagues during two short field trips in 2021. Spiders were hand-picked. A total of 434 specimens were collected. Specimens were collected from seven localities in southern Dagestan. Details of the sampled localities and their habitats are provided below. In the list of recorded spiders given below, each name is followed by a number (in brackets) corresponding to the locality and by a letter corresponding to the habitat from which it was collected. If the habitat is unknown, only the locality number is provided in parentheses. Species recorded from Dagestan for the first time are marked with one asterisk (*), and those new to the Russian fauna are marked

with two (**). The specimens were photographed using an Olympus DP74 camera mounted on an Olympus SZX16 stereomicroscope at Altai State University (Barnaul, Russia). Specimens were photographed in a Petri dish. The bottom of the dish was lined with white cotton and filled with ethanol. Image stacks were montaged using Zerene Stacker software (Zerene Systems, USA). The epigynes were macerated in an aqueous potassium hydroxide solution. Live specimens and habitats were photographed with a Canon PowerShot SX620 HS camera. All measurements are given in millimeters. The lengths of the leg segments were measured on the dorsal side. Leg measurements are presented as: total length (femur, patella, tibia, metatarsus, tarsus). The descriptive terminology and format follow Marusik & Guseinov (2003) and Gündüz (2023), with the following modification: ventral spines are listed in proximal-to-distal pairs. The terminology and format for the redescription follow Fomichev (2021). The studied material is deposited in the Institute of Systematics and Ecology of Animals SB RAS, Novosibirsk, Russia (ISEA; curator G.N. Azarkina). The distribution map was generated using SimpleMappr (Shorthouse 2010) and Mapbox (<https://www.mapbox.com>).

Abbreviations: AER – anterior eye row, ALE – anterior lateral eye, AME – anterior median eye, d – dorsal, Fe – femur, Mt – metatarsus, p – prolateral, Pa – patella, PER – posterior eye row, PLE – posterior lateral eye, PME – posterior median eye, r – retrolateral, Ta – tarsus, Ti – tibia, v – ventral.

List of collecting localities:

- 1/1. Sarykum Dune, 43°00'N, 47°14'E, h=70–300 m, 27–29 April 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov, R.V. Yakovlev.
- 1/2. Ditto, 10–11 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov.
- 1/3. Ditto, 9–12 August 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, E.A. Nepaeva.
2. Vanashimakhi Village, 42°23'N, 47°35'E, h=800 m, 6 May 2021, leg. Y.V. Dyachkov.
3. Gunib Village, 42°24'N, 46°55'E, h=1700–2000 m, 6–8 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov.
4. Tsudakhar Village, 42°20'N, 47°10'E, h=1100–1300 m, 8–9 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, R.V. Yakovlev.
5. Sirtych Village, 41°49'N, 48°10'E, h=200–400 m, 3–4 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, R.V. Yakovlev.
6. Novokayakent Village, 42°20'N, 48°04'E, h=–19 m, 5 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev.
7. Samur Forest, 41°52'N, 48°33'E, h=–30–0 m, 29 April – 2 May 2021, leg. A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov.

Habitats:

- (a) Sandy desert
- (b) Stony semi-desert
- (c) Stony steppe
- (d) Stony shiblyak scrubland with rocks
- (e) Mixed mountain forest
- (f) Liana forest
- (g) Meadow
- (h) Sandy seashore
- (i) Synanthropic habitat

Results

Description of the new species

Family Desidae Pocock, 1895

Comments. Desidae is a relatively small family consisting of 323 extant species in 63 genera (World Spider Catalog 2025). The family has a worldwide distribution, but is best represented in the southern hemisphere, especially in New Zealand and Australia (World Spider Catalog 2025). Only four genera are known from the Palaearctic. Four species of *Cedicoides* Charitonov, 1946 occur in the southern part of Central Asia (Fet 1993, Marusik & Guseinov 2003). *Cedicus* Simon, 1875 is confirmed to occur only in Turkey and Israel (Nentwig et al. 2025). Nentwig et al. (2025) note that the record of *C. flavipes* Simon, 1875 from Croatia requires confirmation. The species *Cedicus bucculentus* Simon, 1889 (from the Himalayas), *C. dubius* Strand, 1907 (from Japan), and *C. pumilus* Thorell, 1895 (from Myanmar) were described from female specimens and have not been illustrated or redescribed since (World Spider Catalog 2025). These species may have been misplaced (Marusik & Guseinov 2003). *Desis japonica* Yaginuma, 1956 from southern Japan is the only representative of the genus in the Palaearctic (Yaginuma 1956). Finally, *Paracedicus* Fet, 1993 is the most widespread representative of the family in the Palaearctic. Species of this genus are distributed from Turkey to the Kyzylkum Desert in southern Kazakhstan (Gündüz 2023, Nekhaeva et al. 2024). All Palaearctic desids, except for the intertidal *D. japonica*, inhabit arid environments (Marusik & Guseinov 2003).

***Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n.**

<http://zoobank.org/E76F336D-BA93-49AB-A6FF-78B91143D090>

Figures 1–9, 64

Type material. **Holotype** ♀ (ISEA, 001.9412), RUSSIA: Republic of Dagestan, near Sarykum Dune, 43°00'N, 47°14'E, stony steppe, 70–300 m, 27–29.04.2021 (A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov, R.V. Yakovlev). **Paratype:** 1 ♀ (ISEA, 001.9413), together with the holotype.

Etymology. The species is named in honor of Alexander V. Ponomarev (Rostov-on-Don, Russia), in recognition of his significant contributions to the study of spiders in Dagestan and the Caucasus.

Diagnosis. The female of the new species is similar to that of *P. feti* Marusik & Guseinov, 2003 from Azerbaijan. Both species have a rectangular median plate (MP) and thin, straight copulatory ducts (CD) that are strongly diverge posteriorly. The female of *P. ponomarevi* sp. n. differs from that of *P. feti* in having a fovea (F) that is twice as wide as the median plate (MP) (vs. almost as wide as the MP; cf. Figs 6–8 and fig. 7 in Marusik & Guseinov (2003)) and in having circular receptacles (R) (vs. kidney-shaped; cf. Fig. 9 and fig. 8 in the same paper).

Description. Female (holotype) (Figs 1–9). Total length 8.2. Carapace: 3.25 long, 2.4 wide. Sternum: 1.9 long, 1.4 wide. Eye sizes and interdistances: AME 0.10, ALE 0.13, PME 0.09, PLE 0.10, ALE–AME 0.10, AME–AME 0.06, ALE–PLE 0.09, PLE–PME 0.21, PME–PME 0.17, AME–PME 0.10, AER 0.67, PER 0.90. Promargin of cheliceral furrow with 6 teeth (the sub-proximal one is the largest); retromargin with 5 teeth (the proximal one is the largest) (Fig. 5). Pars thoracica light brown; pars cephalica brown. Chelicerae dark brown, almost black. Endites and labium brown. Sternum and coxae yellow-brown. Palps and legs brown, with leg I darker than the others. Abdomen dark gray; venter yellow-gray. Spinnerets yellow. Length of leg segments: I: 7.29 (2.25, 1.13, 1.63, 1.38, 0.90); II: 6.79 (2.08, 1.10, 1.38, 1.40, 0.83); III: 5.99 (1.85, 0.98, 1.08, 1.28, 0.80); IV: 7.87 (2.23, 1.18, 1.83, 1.73, 0.90). Spinination of legs: I: Fe d2 p1; Pa 0; Ti p1 v2-2-2; Mt p1 v2-2-2; Ta 0. II: Fe d2 p1; Pa 0; Ti v1-1-2; Mt p1 v2-2-2; Ta 0. III: Fe d2 p2 r1; Pa p1 r1; Ti d1 p2 r2 v2-2-2; Mt p4 r4 v2-2-2; Ta p1. IV: Fe d2 r1; Pa r1; Ti r2 v2-2-2; Mt p2 r4 v2-2-2; Ta p1 r2.

Epigyne as shown in Figs 6–9. Epigynal plate (EP) as long as wide, densely covered with setae. Fovea (F) oval, 3 times wider than long. Median plate (MP) rectangular, twice wider than long. Copulatory ducts (CD) arcuate, inclined, almost twice shorter than EP. Receptacles (R) circular, closely spaced.

Male. Unknown.

Distribution. The species is known only from the type locality (Fig. 64).

Comments. The new species extends the known range of the genus and family within the Palaearctic approximately 3° to the north. Together with *P. feti* from the Apsheron Peninsula (Azerbaijan), the new species defines the northern distributional limit for both the genus and the entire family in the Palaearctic. Like other Palaearctic desids, *P. ponomarevi* sp. n. inhabits arid environments.

Figures 1–5. Holotype female of *Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n.: 1 – general appearance, dorsal; 2 – ditto, ventral; 3 – cephalic part, anterior; 4 – spinnerets, ventral; 5 – left chelicera, posterior. Scale bars: 2 mm (1–2); 0.2 mm (3–5).

Figures 6–9. Epigyne of holotype female of *Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n.: **6** – intact, ventral; **7** – with the setae removed, ventral; **8** – macerated, ventral; **9** – macerated, dorsal. Abbreviations: CD – copulatory duct, EP – epigynal plate, F – fovea, MP – median plate, R – receptacle (the left receptacle is outlined with a dotted line). Scale bars: 0.2 mm.

Redescription

Lycosidae Sundevall, 1833

Genus *Aulonia* C. L. Koch, 1847

Comments. *Aulonia* is a genus of wolf spiders restricted to the West Palaearctic and comprising only two species. The generotype, *A. albimana* (Walckenaer, 1805), is widespread in Europe, with a range extending from Norway to Spain. This species is also found in Turkey and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2025). *Aulonia albimana* has been reported from the mountainous region of Dagestan (Talgi Canyon) (Ponomarev et al. 2019).

***Aulonia kratochvili* Dunin, Buchar & Absolon, 1986**

Figures 10–18

Aulonia kratochvili Dunin, Buchar & Absolon, 1986: 28, f. 1–7 (♂♀).*A. kratochvili*: Seropian et al., 2025: 75, f. 32–35 (♂♀).

For the full list of 9 taxonomic entries see World Spider Catalog (2025).

Material examined. 1♂ 1♀ (ISEA, 001.9414), RUSSIA: Republic of Dagestan, Samur Forest, 41°52'N, 48°33'E, liana forest, –30–0 m, 29.04–02.05.2021 (A.A. Fomichev, Y.V. Dyachkov).

Diagnosis. The male of *A. kratochvili* can be distinguished from that of the generotype by: (1) a cymbial tip as long as the tegulum (T) (vs. half the length in the generotype), and (2) a large tegular apophysis (TA) that is twice as long as T and bent at a 90° angle (vs. an almost straight TA that is nearly as long as T; cf. Figs 11–15 and fig. 207b in Almquist (2006)). The female of *A. kratochvili* differs from that of *A. albimana* in: (1) having a triangular septum (S) (vs. an almost square one; cf. Fig. 17 and fig. 207e in the same paper), (2) having the internal (IR) and external (ER) heads of the receptacles directed toward each other (vs. directed anteriorly), and (3) having the short and curved copulatory ducts (CD) (vs. long and straight; cf. Fig. 18 and fig. 207f in the same paper).

Redescription. Male (Figs 10–15). Total length 4.75. Carapace: 2.43 long, 1.63 wide. Coloration. Carapace dark brown, with white setae on the margins and a thin median stripe. Eye field almost black. Chelicerae and labium dark brown. Endites, sternum, and coxae I brown; coxae II–IV yellow. Palpal patellae yellow and covered with white setae; remaining palpal segments brown. Legs yellow, with the femur of leg I dark brown. Abdomen dark gray with a thin white median stripe. The venter of the abdomen and spinnerets yellow. Length of leg segments: I: 8.81 (2.25, 0.88, 2.13, 2.20, 1.35); II: 6.36 (1.78, 0.75, 1.38, 1.50, 0.95); III: 6.08 (1.70, 0.65, 1.28, 1.60, 0.85); IV: 9.19 (2.43, 0.78, 2.15, 2.68, 1.15). Spination of legs: I: Fe d1-1-1 p0-0-1 r0-0-1; Ti v2-2-2; Mt p0-1-0 v2-2-0. II: Fe d1-1-1 p1-0-1 r0-0-1; Ti p1-0-1 r0-0-1 v1-2-1; Mt p1-1-0 v2-2-0. III: Fe d1-1-1 p0-1-1 r0-1-1; Pa d1 p1; Ti d1-0-1 p1-0-1 r0-1-1 v1-1-2; Mt p1-1-0 r0-1-0 v1-2-0. IV: Fe d1-1-1 p0-0-1 r0-0-1; Pa d1; Ti d1-0-1 p1-0-1 r1-0-1 v2-2-2; Mt p1-1-0 r1-1-0 v2-0-2.

Palp as shown in Figs 11–15. Femur 1.8 times longer than patella. Patella 1.2 times longer than tibia. Tibia 2.6 times shorter than cymbium. Cymbium 2 times longer than wide. Tip of cymbium 1.3 times shorter than bulb. Bulb as long as wide. Subtegulum (St) located medially. Tegulum (T) 1.3 times wider than long. Sperm duct (SD) transverse in ventral view. Tegular apophysis (TA) with basal (BA) and apical (AA) arms. BA beak-shaped. AA triple-peaked. Embolic division (ED) almost entirely concealed by tegulum (T). Conductor (C) membranous, poorly visible. Tip of embolus (E) directed prolaterad.

Figures 10–18. *Aulonia kratochvili*: **10** – general appearance of male, dorsal; **11** – male palp, ventral; **12** – ditto, retrolateral; **13** – bulb, prolateral; **14** – ditto, ventral; **15** – ditto, retrolateral; **16** – general appearance of female, dorsal; **17** – epigyne, ventral; **18** – ditto, dorsal. Abbreviations: AA – apical arm of tegular apophysis, AP – anterior pocket, BA – basal arm of tegular apophysis, C – conductor, CD – copulatory duct, E – embolus, ED – embolic division, EP – epigynal plate, ER – external head of receptacle, IR – internal head of receptacle, L – lip of epigyne, S – septum, SD – sperm duct, St – subtegulum, T – tegulum, TA – tegular apophysis. Scale bars: 2 mm (**10**, **16**); 0.2 mm (**11–15**, **17–18**).

Female (Figs 16–18). Total length 5.1. Carapace: 2.3 long, 1.6 wide. Coloration as in the male. Length of leg segments: I: 6.54 (1.83, 0.80, 1.53, 1.40, 0.98); II: 5.64 (1.63, 0.73, 1.20, 1.25, 0.83); III: 5.65 (1.68, 0.63, 1.18, 1.38, 0.78); IV: 8.51 (2.28, 0.75, 2.05, 2.38, 1.05). Spination of legs: I: Fe d1-1-1 p0-0-1 r0-0-1; Ti v2-2-2; Mt p0-1-0 v2-2-0. II: Fe d1-1-1 p0-0-1 r0-0-1; Ti p1-0-1 v1-2-0; Mt p0-1-0 v2-2-0. III: Fe d1-1-1 p1-0-1 r0-0-1; Pa d1; Ti d1-0-1 p1-0-1 r0-0-1 v1-1-2; Mt p1-1-0 r1-1-0 v2-2-0. IV: Fe d1-1-1 p0-1-1 r0-0-1; Pa d1; Ti d1-0-1 p1-0-1 r0-1-1 v1-1-2; Mt p1-1-0 r1-1-0 v2-0-2.

Epigyne as shown in Figs 17–18. Epigynal plate (EP) 1.6 times wider than long. Fovea (F) low, arcuate, 3.8 times wider than long. Lips of epigyne (L) diverging posteriorly. Septum (S) triangular. Anterior pockets (AP) paired, irregularly shaped. Copulatory ducts (CD) smoothly curved. Receptacles with two heads. External heads of receptacles (ER) equal in size to internal (IR).

Distribution. The range of this species extends from Greece through Israel, Georgia, and Azerbaijan to western Turkmenistan (Dunin et al. 1986, Zonstein et al. 2015, Seropian et al. 2025). This species has not been previously reported from Russia, including Dagestan.

Comments. Despite numerous papers on this unusual wolf spider, the existing descriptions remain incomplete. The male habitus and a dissected bulb in ventral view have never been illustrated. In addition, no data were provided on the measurements of the leg segments and spination. To address this gap, I provide digital images and a redescription.

List of species

Family Agelenidae (1 species)

Pireneitega spasskyi (Charitonov, 1946): 3♀ [3e], 1♀ [3i], 4♀ [3].

Distribution. The species is distributed from northeastern Turkey through Georgia and Azerbaijan to Dagestan (Kovblyuk et al. 2013, Türkeş et al. 2022).

Family Amaurobiidae (1 species)

**Amaurobius fenestralis* (Ström, 1768): 2♂ 4♀ [3i].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Central Europe to Central Asia (Thaler & Knoflach 1998, Mikhailov 2024), but had not been previously reported from Dagestan.

Family Anyphaenidae (1 species)

Anyphaena accentuata (Walckenaer, 1802): 2♂ [7i].

Distribution. The species is widespread from Europe to Central Asia and Iran (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Family Araneidae (5 species)

Agalenatea redii (Scopoli, 1763): 1♂ 2♀ [1/1].

Distribution. The species is widespread from the Azores to Central Asia, with its range extending eastward to China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Argiope lobata (Pallas, 1772): 1♀ [1/3].

Distribution. This species is widespread throughout the (sub)tropical and temperate regions of the Old World, ranging from southern Europe to China and southward to South Africa (Ibrahimi et al. 2024, World Spider Catalog 2025).

***Cyclosa algerica* Simon, 1885: 1♂ [4g]; Figs 19–21.

Distribution. The species is widespread from the Western Mediterranean to northern Iran (World Spider Catalog 2025). Although the species is known from adjacent Azerbaijan (Nuruyeva et al. 2024a), it had not been reported from Dagestan or Russia previously. For this reason, photographs of the general appearance of the male and its palp are provided.

Larinioides ixobolus (Thorell, 1873): 1♀ [6i].

Distribution. The species occurs from Western Europe to Central Asia (Šestáková et al. 2014).

Nuctenea umbratica (Clerck, 1757): 2♀ [7i].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Europe to Azerbaijan and Iran (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Family Atypidae (1 species)

Atypus muralis Bertkau, 1890: 1juv. [4c]; Fig. 63.

Distribution. The species is distributed from Central Europe to Turkmenistan (World Spider Catalog 2025). It is widespread in the Caucasus and Transcaucasia (Nuruyeva et al. 2024b).

Comments. Only three species of *Atypus* occur in the Western Palaearctic: *A. affinis* Eichwald, 1830, *A. muralis* and *A. piceus* (Sulzer, 1776) (Nuruyeva et al. 2024b). The first and last species, which are found mainly in Western and Central Europe, do not occur in the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2025). *Atypus muralis* is the only representative of its genus and family in the Caucasus. Therefore, the juvenile specimen can be confidently assigned to *A. muralis*. Representatives of this genus live in burrows lined with silken tubes that have both subterranean and above-ground sections (Li et al. 2025, Wu et al. 2025). Due to the lack of high-quality photographs of the *A. muralis* web in the literature, a digital photograph is provided here.

Family Cheiracanthiidae (2 species)

Cheiracanthium montanum L. Koch, 1877: 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. Its distribution ranges from Spain to Iran (Zamani et al. 2024b).

Cheiracanthium virescens (Sundevall, 1833): 2♂ [3i], 1♂ [7f], 2♀ [7i].

Distribution. Its range extends from Europe to China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Family Clubionidae (3 species)

Clubiona caucasica Mikhailov & Otto, 2017: 1♂ [3i]; Figs 22–24.

Distribution. The species is distributed from northern Turkey through the Caucasus to Azerbaijan and Dagestan (Mikhailov et al. 2017; Ponomarev & Shmatko 2023).

Comments. The species has a narrow range and is known from only two taxonomic entries (World Spider Catalog 2025). Therefore, photographs of the general appearance of a male and its palp are provided.

Clubiona corticalis (Walckenaer, 1802): 2♀ [3i].

Distribution. Its distribution spans from the Iberian Peninsula to the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2025).

**Clubiona subsultans* Thorell, 1875: 1♂ [3i].

Distribution. This species has a Euro-Baikalian nemoral range, extending from Europe to Mongolia; records from Japan are considered doubtful (Marusik et al. 2000). Although the species has been recorded in the Northern Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it had not been reported from Dagestan.

Family Desidae (1 species)

***Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n. (see description of the new species above): 2♀ [1/1c]; Figs 1–9, 64.

Family Dysderidae (3 species)

Dysdera daghestanica Dunin, 1991: 1♂ 1♀ [1/2c], 1♂ 1♀ [2], 2♂ 4♀ [3].

Distribution. This species has a disjunctive range in the North Caucasus, with populations in Krasnodar Krai (western Caucasus) and Dagestan (eastern Caucasus) (Zamani & Marusik 2024).

Dysdera ukrainensis Charitonov, 1956: 2♂ 10♀ [7f], 3♀ [7i]; Fig. 59.

Distribution. The species has a Ponto-Caspian distribution (Abdurakhmanov et al. 2012).

Harpactea modesta Dunin, 1991: 7♂ 8♀ [7f].

Distribution. The species is endemic to the Caucasus and Transcaucasia, with confirmed records from Dagestan, Azerbaijan, and Georgia (Seropian et al. 2023).

Family Gnaphosidae (17 species)

Drassodes lapidosus (Walckenaer, 1802): 1♂ [1/1], 1♂ [1/2c], 1♂ [1/2], 7♂ [3c], 3♂ [3i], 3♂ 1♀ [4c], 1♂ [7i].

Distribution. It has a Trans-Palaeartic polyzonal range (Nentwig et al. 2025; World Spider Catalog 2025).

Drassyllus crimeaensis Kovblyuk, 2003: 1♀ [5b].

Distribution. Its range extends from the Balkan Peninsula through the southern part of the Russian Plain to Azerbaijan (Polchaninova et al. 2021).

Drassyllus praeficus (L. Koch, 1866): 1♀ [1/1c], 1♀ [5b].

Distribution. It has a West Palaeartic distribution (Kovblyuk 2003).

Drassyllus pusillus (C. L. Koch, 1833): 1♂ [3e], 2♂ [7f].

Distribution. It has a Trans-Eurasian nemoral distribution (Marusik et al. 2000; Nentwig et al. 2025).

Gnaphosa lugubris (C. L. Koch, 1839): 4♂ 2♀ [3c], 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. Its distribution spans from Spain through Central Europe to Iran (Zamani et al. 2024a, Nentwig et al. 2025).

Gnaphosa mongolica Simon, 1895: 1♂ [1/2].

Distribution. It inhabits the steppe zone of Eurasia, with a range extending from Hungary to China (Ovtsharenko et al. 1992).

Gnaphosa steppica Ovtsharenko, Platnick & Song, 1992: 1♂ [3c].

Distribution. It inhabits the steppe zone of Eurasia, including the Caucasus (Ovtsharenko et al. 1992).

**Haplodrassus kulczynskii* Lohmander, 1942: 1♀ [4c].

Distribution. This species has a disjunct West Palaeartic–Far East nemoral-subtropical range, comprising populations from Central Europe to the Urals and from the Russian Far East to the Korean Peninsula (Kovblyuk et al. 2012). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it had not been recorded in Dagestan.

Haplodrassus nabozhenkoi Ponomarev, 2023: 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. The species was recently described from Maidanskoe Village (Ponomarev & Shmatko 2023), located approximately 35 km north-northeast of the new finding in Tsudakhar Village. This finding represents the first record of the species outside its type locality.

Haplodrassus signifer (C. L. Koch, 1839): 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. It has a Circum-Holarctic polyzonal distribution (Marusik et al. 2000).

Marinarozelotes jaxartensis (Kroneberg, 1875): 1♂ [5b].

Distribution. Its native range extends from North Africa to Central Asia. It has also been introduced to Hawaii, North America, South Africa, and East Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Nomisia aussereri (L. Koch, 1872): 1♂ [1/3].

Distribution. Its distribution extends from Morocco through the steppe zone of the Russian Plain and the Caucasus to Mongolia and China (Chatzaki 2010, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Nomisia conigera (Spassky, 1941): 2♂ [1/1c], 1♂ [1/1d], 2♂ [5b].

Distribution. Its range extends from Turkey through Azerbaijan and Dagestan to Tajikistan (Ponomarev et al. 2019).

Nomisia exornata (C. L. Koch, 1839): 2♂ [1/2], 2♂ [5b], 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. Its distribution ranges from Europe to Central Asia (Chatzaki 2010).

**Poecilochroa variana* (C. L. Koch, 1839): 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. It has a Euro-Central Asian steppe range (Tuneva & Esyunin 2002). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it had not been recorded in Dagestan.

Scotophaeus scutulatus (L. Koch, 1866): 1♀ [5b].

Distribution. Its distribution spans from Western Europe to Central Asia (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Zelotes subterraneus (C. L. Koch, 1833): 1♂ 2♀ [7f].

Distribution. Although reported to have a Trans-Palaeartic range (World Spider Catalog 2025), some evidence suggests its distribution may be restricted to Europe (Ponomarev & Shmatko 2019a).

Family Lathyidae (1 species)

Lathys humilis (Blackwall, 1855): 2♂ [3i].

Distribution. Its native range extends from western Europe to the Caucasus and Mazandaran in northern Iran (Marusik et al. 2009). It has also been introduced to Canada (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Family Lycosidae (13 species)

Alopecosa cuneata (Clerck, 1757): 4♂ [3e], 4♂ 1♀ [7f].

Distribution. It has a Trans-Eurasian boreo-nemoral distribution (Marusik et al. 2000; Nentwig et al. 2025).

Alopecosa albofasciata (Brullé, 1832): 1♂ 1♀ [1/1d], 1♂ [1/1], 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. Its distribution extends from the Mediterranean to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Arctosa personata (L. Koch, 1872): 1♂ [5b]; Figs 25–36.

Distribution. The species is known from the southern part of Western Europe and from Dagestan (Ponomarev et al. 2019, Iorio 2023, present data).

Comments. Nentwig et al. (2025) note that the records of this species from Turkey and the Caucasus require confirmation. *Arctosa personata* was recorded in Dagestan from Tarki-Tau Mountain and the Sarykum Dune (both located near Makhachkala) by Ponomarev et al. (2019). According to Nentwig et al. (2025), this species prefers warm, dry, stony habitats. This finding is consistent with our data, as the specimen was collected in a stony semi-desert. The species is easily identifiable by its elongated, pointed and almost straight tegular apophysis. However, the published illustrations lack detailed views of the dissected bulb, the embolic division, and the separated tegulum. Such detailed depictions are essential for the taxonomic study of wolf spiders. Therefore, these illustrations are provided to fill that gap. The range of this species is incorrectly reported in the World Spider Catalog (2025) as being limited to southern Western Europe.

Arctosa ravidata Ponomarev, 2007: 3♂ 2♀ [1/1a], 9♂ 5♀ [7h]; Figs 37–46.

Distribution. The species is distributed in the Caspian Lowland and on the islands of the Northern Caspian Sea, within Dagestan and north-western Kazakhstan (Ponomarev & Shmatko 2019b).

Comments. Among European representatives of the genus *Arctosa* for which ecological data are available, most species inhabit humid environments, often near stagnant or running water (Nentwig et al. 2025). A small number of species inhabit dry habitats, with only *A. ravidata* occurring in true sand deserts far from water. Spiders were collected from areas of bare sand devoid of vegetation on the Sarykum Dune [1/1a] (Fig. 41). The spiders were active only at night. Ponomarev (2007)

notes that *A. ravida* digs burrows 20–30 cm deep in the depressions between dunes, where the sand is saturated with moisture even at shallow depths. In addition to the sandy desert of the Sarykum Dune, this species was also found in the Samur Forest area on the sandy sea coast [7h] (Fig. 46). Specimens from the sandy desert exhibited a yellow, unpatterned coloration (Figs 38, 40), whereas those collected from the sea coast were bluish with a dark pattern on the carapace and abdomen (Figs 43, 45). The copulatory organs were nearly identical between the two series of spiders. Thus, the coloration of *A. ravida* depends on local conditions, presumably on the properties of the substrate.

Figures 19–24. *Cyclosa algerica* (19–21) and *Clubiona caucasica* (22–24): 19, 22 – general appearance of male, dorsal; 20 – ditto, lateral; 21, 24 – male palp, retrolateral; 23 – ditto, ventral. Scale bars: 2 mm (19–20, 22); 0.2 mm (21, 23–24).

Figures 25–30. Male of *Arctosa personata*: 25 – general appearance, dorsal; 26 – palp, ventral; 27 – ditto, retrolateral; 28 – bulb, prolateral; 29 – ditto, ventral; 30 – ditto, retrolateral. Scale bars: 2 mm (25); 0.2 mm (26–30).

***Aulonia kratochvili* Dunin, Buchar & Absolon, 1986 (see above): 1♂ 1♀ [7f]; Figs 10–18.

Hogna radiata (Latreille, 1817): 1♂ [1/3]; Fig. 56.

Distribution. Its distribution ranges from the western Mediterranean to Central Asia, extending southward to Iran (Logunov 2022).

Lycosa praegrandis C. L. Koch, 1836: 1♀ [1/1c], 1♂ 1♀ [1/3]; Fig. 57.

Distribution. This species has an East Mediterranean–Middle Asian range (Logunov 2023).

Mustelicosa dimidiata (Thorell, 1875): 1♂ [1/2], 1♀ [1/3], 3♂ 1♀ [3c], 11♂ 2♀ [4c], 5♂ [4g]; Fig. 55.

Distribution. The species has an East European–Central Asian subboreal range (Yanul et al. 2022).

Pardosa pontica (Thorell, 1875): 1♂ [1/1g].

Distribution. The species is reliably recorded from Kherson Region through Crimea and the Caucasus to south-western Turkmenistan (Zyuzin & Logunov 2000).

Pardosa caucasica Ovtsharenko, 1979: 6♂ 8♀ [3e].

Distribution. Its distribution is restricted to the Caucasus, ranging from Krasnodar Krai to Azerbaijan (Nadolny & Kovblyuk 2012).

Pardosa nebulosa (Thorell, 1872): 8♂ 3♀ [1/1g], 1♂ [7f], 4♀ [7].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Central Europe to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Trochosa terricola Thorell, 1856: 1♂ [3e], 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. It has a Circum-Holarctic, polyzonal range (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Trochosa hispanica Simon, 1870: 4♂ 4♀ [7f].

Distribution. The species is reliably recorded from the Iberian Peninsula to the Mazandaran Province of Iran (Marusik & Nadolny 2020).

Family Mimetidae (1 species)

**Ero furcata* (Villers, 1789): 1♀ [3e].

Distribution. Its range extends from the Azores to Japan, reaching southward to Turkmenistan (World Spider Catalog 2025). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it has not been recorded in Dagestan.

Family Miturgidae (1 species)

Zora spinimana (Sundevall, 1833): 2♀ [3].

Distribution. The species has a Trans-Eurasian, polyzonal range (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Family Philodromidae (2 species)

Rhysdromus timidus Szita & Logunov, 2008: 1♀ [1/1].

Distribution. The species is known from Dagestan, Kazakhstan, and Pakistan (Szita & Logunov 2008, Logunov et al. 2011, Ponomarev et al. 2019).

Thanatus imbecillus L. Koch, 1878: 2♂ [1/1c], 3♂ 2♀ [4c].

Distribution. The species has a Euro-Central Asian subboreal range (Kastrygina & Kovblyuk 2013).

Family Pholcidae (2 species)

Pholcus alticeps Spassky, 1932: 1♂ 3♀ [3i], 4♂ 10♀ [4i], 2♀ [7i]; Fig. 61.

Distribution. It is widespread, ranging from Poland to the Omsk Region in Western Siberia and extending southward to Iran (Huber 2011).

Pholcus crassipalpis Spassky, 1937: 1♂ 2♀ [7f].

Distribution. It is widespread, ranging from Bulgaria to the Orenburg Region of Russia (Huber 2011, Dimitrov & Naumova 2021).

Family Pisauridae (2 species)

Pisaura mirabilis (Clerck, 1757): 2♂ [4g].

Distribution. Its distribution extends from Portugal to the Yenisei River, reaching southward to Northern Africa and Central Asia (Esyunin & Sozontov 2015).

Pisaura novicia (L. Koch, 1878): 1♂ [1/1d], 1♂ [7f], 1♀ [7i].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Eastern Europe to Central Asia (Esyunin & Sozontov 2015).

Comments. Nadolny et al. (2012) reported a sympatric distribution for *P. mirabilis* and *P. novicia* in Crimea, the southern Russian Plain (Rostov Region), and the Caucasus (North Ossetia). Our new data confirm this for Dagestan as well.

Family Salticidae (14 species)

**Aelurillus laniger* Logunov & Marusik, 2000: 1♂ [4c]; Figs 47–54.

Distribution. Its distribution ranges from North Macedonia to the Russian Plain and Crimea, with a further, disjunct occurrence in the Pavlodar and Akmola regions of Kazakhstan (Logunov & Marusik 2000, Mikhailov 2024, Nentwig et al. 2025). The species had not been previously reported from Dagestan specifically, or from the Caucasus in general.

Comments. The new record from Dagestan partially fills a gap in the species' known range. Given that the species is confined to steppe habitats, its range is likely

continuous across the entire Eurasian steppe zone. Future records of *A. laniger* will likely eliminate this apparent disjunction in its range. The species is documented in only a single taxonomic source (World Spider Catalog 2025). Therefore, I provide photographs of the general appearance of the male, as well as the palp and its embolic division.

Aelurillus v-insignitus (Clerck, 1757): 2♂ [4c].

Distribution. This species has a Trans-Eurasian, polyzonal range (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

**Attulus penicillatus* (Simon, 1875): 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. Its distribution ranges from Central Europe to Japan (Logunov 1993). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it has not been recorded in Dagestan.

Attulus relictarius (Logunov, 1998): 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. The species is distributed from the Northern Caucasus through Georgia and Azerbaijan to north-eastern Iran (Logunov 1998, Abdurakhmanov et al. 2012).

Cyrba algerina (Lucas, 1846): 1♂ 2♀ [1/1c], 4♂ 1♀ [5b].

Distribution. The species is distributed from the Canary Islands to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Heliophanus cupreus (Walckenaer, 1802): 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Western Europe to China (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Menemerus taeniatus (L. Koch, 1867): 1♂ [1/3].

Distribution. The species is native from the Mediterranean region to the Caucasus and has been introduced to Argentina (Nentwig et al. 2025). The Caucasus represents the eastern limit of its range (Rakov & Logunov 1997).

Pellenes geniculatus (Simon, 1868): 1♂ 4♀ [4c].

Distribution. Its distribution extends from Southern Europe to Central Asia and southward to South Africa (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Pellenes nigrociliatus (Simon, 1875): 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. The species is distributed from the Canary Islands through Europe and the Caucasus to Central Asia and China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Pellenes seriatus (Thorell, 1875): 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Southern Europe to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Philaeus chryrops (Poda, 1761): 1♂ [1/1c], 1♀ [1/1d], 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. The species has a Trans-Palaeartic nemoral range (Marusik et al. 2000).

Phlegra cinereofasciata (Simon, 1868): 2♀ [4c].

Distribution. The species is reliably recorded from Portugal to Dagestan (Azarkina 2004, Nentwig et al. 2025). According to the World Spider Catalog (2025), the species is also present in Central Asia and China. Mikhailov (2024) questions all records of *P. cinereofasciata* from Central Asia and Siberia.

Pseudeuophrys obsoleta (Simon, 1868): 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. Its range extends from Europe (excluding Scandinavia) to the Russian Far East and China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Salticus tricinctus (C. L. Koch, 1846): 1♂ [1/1].

Distribution. The species has an Eastern Mediterranean–Central Asian distribution, ranging from Turkey to southern Kazakhstan and Afghanistan (Logunov 2015).

Family Scytodidae (1 species)

Scytodes thoracica (Latreille, 1802): 1♀ [3i], 1♀ [5b], 3♂ 14♀ [7i]; Fig. 60.

Distribution. This species has a cosmopolitan distribution due to widespread introduction (Rozwałka & Czaja 2021, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Comments. This species was collected not only in synanthropic habitats [3i, 7i] (Fig. 60) but also outdoors in a stony semi-desert [5b].

Family Segestriidae (1 species)

Segestria bavarica C. L. Koch, 1843: 7♂ 10♀ [3i], 1♀ [4c], 8♂ 2♀ [4i]; Fig. 58.

Distribution. This species is widespread from Western Europe to Turkey and the Caucasus (Nentwig et al. 2025).

Comments. Almost all specimens of *S. bavarica* were collected from crevices in old stone walls (Fig. 66). The mating process of this species was observed (Fig. 58). Mating occurred at night, approximately 3 cm from the female's web. The female was suspended upside down by several silk threads, with the male positioned above her. The spiders did not respond to external stimuli. A review of *S. bavarica* observations on the iNaturalist website (<https://www.inaturalist.org>) revealed multiple records from Belgium and the Netherlands, in which spiders were mating in the same position.

Family Sparassidae (1 species)

Micrommata virescens (Clerck, 1757): 1♂ 1♀ [7i].

Distribution. The distribution ranges from the Iberian Peninsula to Japan (Jäger 2023).

Family Theridiidae (7 species)

Asagena phalerata (Panzer, 1801): 1♂ 1♀ [7f].

Distribution. This species has a Trans-Palaeartic bore-nemoral range (Marusik et al. 2000).

**Crustulina guttata* (Wider, 1834): 2♂ 1♀ [4c], 1♂ 1♀ [7f].

Distribution. It has a Trans-Eurasian polyzonal range (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it has not been recorded from Dagestan.

Latrodectus tredecimguttatus (Rossi, 1790): 1♀ [1/3]; Fig. 62.

Distribution. Its distribution extends from the Mediterranean to China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Figures 31–36. Details of the bulb of *Arctosa personata*: 31 – tegulum, prolateral; 32 – ditto, ventral; 33 – ditto, retrolateral; 34 – embolic division, prolateral; 35 – ditto, ventral; 36 – ditto, retrolateral. Scale bars: 0.2 mm.

Figures 37–46. *Arctosa ravidus* from the sandy desert in Sarykum Dune (37–41) and from sandy sea coast from Samur Forest (42–46): 37, 42 – bulb, ventral; 38, 43 – live male in habitat; 39, 44 – epigyne, ventral; 40, 45 – live female in habitat; 41, 46 – habitat. Scale bars: 0.2 mm.

Steatoda castanea (Clerck, 1757): 3♀ [3i].

Distribution. This species is distributed from Europe to China and has been introduced to Canada (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Steatoda paykulliana (Walckenaer, 1806): 2♀ [1/1c], 2♂ [3i], 2♂ 2♀ [5b], 1♂ [6i], 1♂ 2♀ [7f], 3♂ [7i].

Distribution. It is distributed from the Mediterranean to Central Asia and India (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Steatoda triangulosa (Walckenaer, 1802): 2♀ [1/1c], 2♀ [5b], 2♀ [6i], 6♀ [7i].

Distribution. This species has a Trans-Palaeartic polyzonal range and has been introduced to the Americas, the Canary Islands, and South Africa (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

**Theridion mystaceum* L. Koch, 1870: 1♂ 1♀ [3i], 1♂ 1♀ [6i].

Distribution. Its range extends from Europe to southern Siberia and China (World Spider Catalog 2025). Although the species is known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it has not been recorded from Dagestan.

Family Thomisidae (12 species)

Bassaniodes tristrami (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1872): 10♀ [1/1c], 8♀ [1/1d], 1♀ [1/1], 1♀ [1/2], 2♀ [5b].

Distribution. The species is distributed from Greece, through the Caucasus and Central Asia, to India (Tripathi et al. 2023, World Spider Catalog 2025).

**Ozyptila pullata* (Thorell, 1875): 1♂ [4c].

Distribution. According to the World Spider Catalog (2025), this species is considered European. According to Mikhailov (2024), *O. pullata* is widespread, with its range extending as far as Western Siberia. Although the species is also known from the Caucasus (Mikhailov 2024), it has not been recorded from Dagestan.

Ozyptila scabricula (Westring, 1851): 1♂ [4g].

Distribution. This species is distributed from Western Europe to Korea and Japan (Kim et al. 2016, Nentwig et al. 2025).

Pistius truncatus (Pallas, 1772): 1♂ [4g].

Distribution. Its distribution spans from Europe to the Russian Far East (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Synema ornatum (Thorell, 1875): 1♂ 1♀ [4c].

Distribution. The species occurs from the Balkan Peninsula to the Orenburg Region of Russia (Ponomarev & Shmatko 2022).

Tmarus punctatissimus (Simon, 1870): 1♂ [4g].

Distribution. This species has a disjunct distribution, occurring from Portugal to France and from the Caucasus to Korea and Japan (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Xysticus bifasciatus C. L. Koch, 1837: 1♂ [3e].

Distribution. This species is distributed from Europe to China (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Figures 47–54. Male of *Aelurillus laniger*: 47 – general appearance, dorsal; 48 – cephalic part, anterior; 49 – palp, ventral; 50 – ditto, retrolateral; 51 – embolic division, dorsal; 52 – ditto, prolateral; 53 – ditto, ventral; 54 – ditto, retrolateral. Scale bars: 2 mm (47); 0.2 mm (48–54).

Figures 55–63. Live specimens in the nature (55–62) and tube of *Atypus muralis* (63). 55 – male of *Mustelicosa dimidiata*, 56 – male of *Hogna radiata*, 57 – female of *Lycosa praegrandis*, 58 – mating *Segestria bavarica*, 59 – female of *Dysdera ukrainensis*, 60 – female of *Scytodes thoracica*, 61 – female of *Pholcus alticeps*, 62 – female of *Latrodectus tredecimguttatus*.

Figures 64–66. Habitats in collecting localities: 64 – stony steppe near Sarykum Dune, habitat of *Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n.; 65 – Samur liana forest; 66 – synanthropic habitat in Tsudakhar Village.

Figures 67–68. Collecting localities in Dagestan: 1 – Sarykum Dune; 2 – Vanashimakhi Village; 3 – Gunib Village; 4 – Tsudakhar Village; 5 – Sirtych Village; 6 – Novokayakent Village; 7 – Samur Forest. The frame of Fig. 68 refers to the content of Fig. 67.

Xysticus kochi Thorell, 1872: 2♂ [1/1g], 1♀ [1/1], 1♂ [5].

Distribution. It ranges from Europe to Central Asia (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Xysticus laetus Thorell, 1875: 2♂ [7f], 1♂ [5].

Distribution. Its distribution extends from Italy, through the Balkan Peninsula and Asia Minor, to the eastern Caucasus and Iran (Logunov 2006, Nentwig et al. 2025).

Xysticus lanio C. L. Koch, 1835: 1♀ [7f].

Distribution. Its range extends from Western Europe to Middle Siberia, with a southern extension to Turkmenistan (Nentwig et al. 2025, World Spider Catalog 2025).

Xysticus luctator L. Koch, 1870: 1♂ [7f].

Distribution. It is distributed from Europe to southern Siberia and Kazakhstan (World Spider Catalog 2025).

Xysticus spasskyi Utochkin, 1968: 1♂ [3e].

Distribution. The species occurs from Crimea, through the Caucasus, to Azerbaijan (Marusik & Azarkina 2016).

Discussion

The list above includes 93 spider species from 23 families. Twelve species were recorded from Dagestan for the first time: *Aelurillus laniger*, *Amaurobius fenestralis*, *Attulus penicillatus*, *Aulonia kratochvili*, *Clubiona subsultans*, *Crustulina guttata*, *Cyclosa algerica*, *Ero furcata*, *Haplodrassus kulczynskii*, *Poecilochroa variana*, *T. mystaceum*, and *Ozyptila pullata*. The absence of most of these widespread species from previous records in Dagestan is likely due to insufficient study of the region. Two species, *Aulonia kratochvili* and *Cyclosa algerica*, are reported from Russia for the first time. One family, Desidae, is newly recorded for the Russian fauna, represented by the new species *Paracedicus ponomarevi* sp. n. Including the results of this study, the spider fauna of Dagestan comprises at least 475 species from 33 families. Although the spider fauna of Dagestan is relatively well-studied, it still holds potential for further research. The monograph on the spiders of Dagestan includes a map of the collection localities (Abdurakhmanov et al. 2012: Fig. 3). This map shows that most sampling sites are located in the low mountains and midlands of southern, mountainous Dagestan. The plains of northern Dagestan were largely unsurveyed. Ponomarev et al. (2019) addressed this gap with a study of the spider fauna of Dagestan that included the lowland regions. However, a significant gap remains in the knowledge of Dagestan's spider fauna. This gap corresponds to the highlands of the Main Caucasian Range in southwestern Dagestan, along the borders with Azerbaijan and Georgia. It can be predicted that this region will be the source of new spider species descriptions in the future, particularly for the families Gnaphosidae and Lycosidae. The discovery of new species in the genus *Parasyrisca* Schenkel, 1963 (Gnaphosidae) is highly probable. Spiders of this genus are highly diverse in the alpine zone of the Caucasus and are characterized by narrow local endemism (Ovtsharenko et al. 1995a). To date, they have not been recorded in Dagestan. Collecting spiders in the deep stone scree of the mountainous regions of the republic could yield new species of Nesticidae, a family currently represented in Dagestan by only a single species (Fomichev et al. 2022). Furthermore, the list of spider families recorded from Dagestan is likely to be expanded. Representatives of the family Filistatidae, which have not yet been recorded in Dagestan, occur in neighboring Azerbaijan (Marusik & Zonstein 2014). Additionally, a representative of the family Palpimanidae is known from the eastern desert region of Azerbaijan (Marusik & Guseinov 2003). These families may also be discovered in the lowland desert region of Dagestan, which is wedged between the mountains and the Caspian Sea. In conclusion, the understudied state of the arthropod fauna of Dagestan is evidenced by the fact that research on both relatively well-studied groups (e.g., Lepidoptera) and less diverse groups (e.g., Chilopoda) continues to yield significant faunistic novelties (Dyachkov et al. 2022, Yakovlev et al. 2022).

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